

TEACHING RUSSIAN AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE USING INNOVATIVE METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES

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ABSTRACT

This article reveals the problems of teaching Russian as a foreign language. It examines modern methods and approaches of teaching the Russian language. The article also discusses the goals of innovative education, the positive aspects of the use of innovative technologies in education. The need for an innovative approach to both the content of the material and the right choice of technologies is emphasized.

Introduction

The 21st century is the century of developments, from this point of view, in the modern world, the problems of education can no longer be treated as before. Therefore, in the field of education, and in general in all areas, such concepts as "innovation", "innovative technologies", "innovative approach" are very relevant. In the modern methodology of teaching Russian as a foreign language, innovative technologies are most often used. And this is no coincidence. Modern society, modern attitude to life impose modern approaches to learning. Why is great attention being paid to the use of innovative technologies in

education at the present time? This is primarily due to the fact that in modern education the place of the teacher has changed, his role in the learning process. Now, in the process of teaching, the teacher should not give ready-made knowledge to students, but teach them to acquire knowledge, to work on themselves. Teach them to read books as much as possible and draw their own conclusions. And the teacher in this process points the way to the acquisition of knowledge, serves as a "guiding star". And this is very important when students learn Russian as a foreign language.

“Teaching the Russian language in modern conditions requires completely new, innovative approaches from the language teacher both to the content of the lesson and to the choice of educational technologies, effective teaching methods, and diagnosing the level of proficiency in Russian as a non-native language.

Main part Innovative approaches to teaching the Russian language in a multi-ethnic environment are based primarily not only on the awareness of the importance of the problem of the low level of students' preparation in the Russian language, the understanding that the reason for poor knowledge of the Russian language is primarily related to the problem of the student's social and psychological adaptation to a new culture, to new traditions, values, guidelines, but also on mastering the principles of an activity approach to teaching Russian as a non-native language.

An innovative approach to teaching the Russian language as non-native actual "...". This requires the dictionary specialist to choose effective forms of working with texts of different types and styles of speech, listening, speaking. In this regard, the lessons of speech development, the lesson of complex text analysis require special attention. Create your own text, interpret the text proposed for analysis by students. To express your thoughts in a non-native language, it is not enough to know the rules. To do this, you first need to expand the active dictionary. How to do it in Russian lessons? The system of pre-text exercises, which is typical for the methodology of teaching a foreign language, helps. "[2] Therefore, each philologist should master innovative teaching methods well and

understand what the very concept of “innovative learning” means.

Innovative education (from the English innovation - innovation) is a new approach to learning, which includes a personal approach, the fundamental nature of education, creativity, professionalism, and the use of the latest technologies. “The relevance of innovative learning lies in the use of student-centered learning, as well as the search for conditions for unlocking the creative potential of the student.

The main goals of innovative learning are:

- development of intellectual, communicative, linguistic and creative abilities of students;
 - formation of personal qualities of students;
 - development of skills that affect educational and cognitive activity and transition to the level of productive creativity;
 - formation of key competencies of students.
- These goals also define the tasks of innovative learning:
- optimization of the educational process;
 - creating an atmosphere of cooperation between the student and the teacher;
 - development of long-term positive motivation for learning;
 - Careful selection of material and methods of its presentation.

Innovative learning is based on the following technologies:

- developing training;
- problem-based learning;
- development of critical thinking;
- technology "Method of projects";
- a differentiated approach to learning;
- creating a situation of success in the lesson;
- information Technology.

The use of these technologies in the classroom has great advantages. The educational process becomes interesting for students, which increases the activity of students, develops the skills to independently acquire knowledge in the process of interaction and search. The quality and strength of the acquired knowledge increases. Research skills and abilities are developed, analytical abilities of students are formed. In parallel with the learning process, there is a development of communicative qualities and the formation of leadership qualities of the individual. [3] Based on this alone, we can understand the great importance of an innovative approach in teaching Russian as a foreign language and how fruitfully they influence the learning process. Therefore, in the process of teaching Russian as a foreign language, every word specialist must use different types of innovative technologies to achieve the goal. "An innovative approach requires every linguist to master the methodology of teaching Russian as a foreign language, understanding that students perceive the laws of the Russian language through the prism of the laws of their native language, and this is the cause of many spelling and even punctuation errors. Such errors are classified as interference. Difficulties in mastering Russian as a non-native language can be divided into three levels:

- difficulties common to any non-Russian
- difficulties for speakers of a certain group of languages (closely related, unrelated)
- difficulties for students of a particular nationality. [2]

To solve such problems during the Russian language classes, it is very effective to use a variety of innovative technologies such as insert, brainstorming, group discussion, reading with stops, "Bloom's Questions", clusters, cinquain, "Advanced Lecture", essay, key terms, didactic game, text research, work with texts and others.

Innovative approaches to teaching the Russian language as foreign students require not only a clear organization of the educational process, but also the ability to correctly and appropriately use innovative and interactive teaching methods.

Conclusion

Thus, an innovative approach to teaching helps the teacher organize the learning process in such a way that the lesson no longer becomes a boring process for the student, but turns the learning process into a game, bringing both benefit and joy, which can ultimately lead the student to success.

In recent decades, much attention has been paid to the use of innovative technologies in the field of education, because, as we said above, innovative teaching approaches make the learning process interesting and entertaining. After all, it was not for nothing that Jan Amos Comenius once wrote: "Hurry to school like a game. She is like that." Based on this, we can say that innovative learning approaches are the most important incentive for learning. Especially, innovative technologies are very productive in teaching Russian as a foreign language.

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